

DEFINITION OF PRAISE IN ENGLISH CULTURE

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Abstract. *In the given article the meaning of praise in English culture, its expression by scientists in the act of speech are described. The article shows that the dictionary definition has its expression in the language. Here the expression of the word praise in English is underlined with examples.*

Keywords: *praise, English culture, politeness, compliment, manipulative, communicative, autonomy, linguacultural.*

It is known that praise occupies a special place in the speech habits of different peoples, but there is no description that reflects its essence.

The importance of praise in English culture is noted by many observers, in particular, according to A. Veibiska, praise should be sincere and real, and not “manipulative.” “Praise is appreciated only if it comes “straight from the heart” and can indicate sincere feelings, and not just a desire to please the recipient” [1].

According to M.A. Kormilisin and G.R. Shamenova, the communicative category of politeness makes it possible to create ethical conditions for successful communication. The main components analyzed include:

- a) readiness to show respect, sympathy, goodwill, attention, help to the interlocutor;
- b) be able to control oneself in expressing negative assessments and feelings and study one’s qualities;
- c) compliance with the rules of behavior accepted in a given society [2].

According to T.V. Larina, one of the most important values of English culture is the autonomy of a person belonging to individualistic cultures. To express the inalienable right of the British to autonomy in the English language, there is the lexeme Privacy [3]. The concept of personal autonomy determines many features of English communicative behavior that are not specific to Uzbek culture.

The need of representatives of English culture to maintain each other's autonomy, to respect and preserve their individuality has led to the emergence of a complex of carefully developed communicative strategies and tactics in the arsenal of this linguistic culture.

At the same time, a certain degree of falsification or influence of the addresser on the addressee is also acceptable for communication between representatives of English culture [4].

It is important to suggest that positive politeness strategies in English culture include compliments, greetings, thanks, apologies and praise.

In English culture, praise is not a pragmatic, but a functional and semantic emotional speech act. From a pragmatic point of view, compliments are one of the types of emotional statements for native English speakers.

The understanding of the meaning of praise by representatives of English culture is similar to that of representatives of Uzbek culture. Analysis of dictionary definitions shows that native English speakers define praise as specific verbal and non-verbal actions, skills of the recipient, as

well as abilities, character traits, etc. of the recipient or a third party, etc. They understand it as an explanation of positive feelings. which arise as a result of their personal qualities.

Praise in English culture is expressed through speech acts of admiration and warm approval [5].

The word praise (praise) has the following expressions in English: *praise, compliment, boast(ing), commend, accolade, flatter, tribute, admiration, adulation, applause, blessing, endorsement, ovation, acclaim, appreciation, eulogy, respects and others.*

Oxford Learner's Dictionary [6] the dictionary gives the following definitions:

Praise

express warm approval or admiration of

We can't praise Chris enough – he did a brilliant job

His latest movie has won high praise from the critics

Commend

to praise somebody/something, especially publicly

She was commended on her handling of the situation

His designs were highly commended by the judges

Boast

to talk in a way that shows you are too proud of something that you have or can do

1. *I don't want to boast, but I can actually speak six languages*

She is always boasting about how wonderful her children are

Dictionary of Merriam Webster [7]:

Praise

to express a favorable judgement of...

A good teacher praises students when they do well

Accolade

an expression of praise

A movie that has drawn accolades from both fans and critics

Cambridge Dictionary [8] the following definition is given in the dictionary:

Praise

to express admiration or approval of the achievements or characteristics of a person or thing

My parents always praised me when I did well at school

Compliment

to praise someone or something

I take it as a compliment when people say I look like my mother

I was just complimenting Robert on his wonderful food

Commend

to formally praise someone or something

The judge commended her for/on her bravery

Flatter

to praise someone in order to make them feel attractive or important, sometimes in a way that is not sincere.

I knew he was only flattering me because he wanted to borrow some money **Tribute**

something that you say, write, or give that shows your respect and admiration for someone, especially on a formal occasion

The minister paid tribute to the men who had fought the blaze

There seem to be many expressions of praise in the English language that have their own nuanced meanings.

The existing meanings are typical for the Uzbek language, but in terms of verbalization, English is more specialized.

The ethical and aesthetic aspects of praise have attracted the attention of not only linguists, but also philosophers and educators. In the words of Alisher Navoi: “Do not let yourself be deceived by the enemy; I don't mean flattery. The enemy's intention is to achieve his evil intention; the goal of the praiser is to humbly accept the gift from you. If you do not praise both of them and do not know how to accept them, then one of them will cease to fulfill its purpose and its activity will be spoiled, and the praise of the other will turn into a joke” [9].

In the works of world thinkers, as well as in folklore, the following views are often found: It is pleasant to hear praise from a person worthy of praise (Gnei Nevi, c. 270-201), Do not trust a person who praises you too much (Japanese proverb): “If you hear, like someone praising someone too much”, “Who is this praise addressed to?” (Miguel de Unamuno (1864-1936)) [10].

Too much praise - too much work (Uzbek folk proverb).

This form of approval, recognition and encouragement, where sincerity is the main condition, is distinguished from flattery, flattery and compliments by a very elegant veil. Socio-mental boundaries are determined by religious, socio-psychological aspects of people's lives. In particular, for the Uzbek people, compliments aimed at appearance are frowned upon for several reasons:

1. Due to the fact that compliments addressed to a woman's appearance, especially her height, are not typical for men, it cannot be said that women are given wide freedom in this regard. In transparent conversations, several patterns are used: sarvkamat (slim and fit), white-white, red-red, flower-shaped, moon-faced, eyebrow-eyed.

2. Praise for children is also limited by the rules: this child is so ugly, don't let your eyes touch.

Eye contact is dangerous not only for children and adults, but also for objects and animals. There are several ways to avoid this, such as saying "don't make eye contact" as soon as you hear a compliment, burning the thread of the person giving the compliment, and lighting incense.

At the same time, I would like to emphasize that the linguocultural description of praise is very unique. People belonging to the Christian religion, including the British, have the custom of crossing their index and middle fingers to avoid eye contact while listening to praise, and of burning a little human or animal hair [11].

Standards of praise and views on the place of use are part of the communication culture of every people.

Praise is a unique, active form of influencing a person. The emergence of the genre of praise involves several components: the addressee of praise (the praiser), the addressee of praise (the one to whom the praise is addressed), the object of praise (the thing being praised), the subject of praise (the one who is praised) the basis of praise, motive (why did the praise arise?), form

(what form was chosen: verbal, non-verbal speech, word form, parameter), understanding of praise, result.

Praise expresses and forms an attitude towards an object, clarifies the emotional description of communication, brings interlocutors closer, and increases attention to the content of communication.

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